

Developing a Triple-System Estimator with List Dependence and Nonresponse

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Abstract

The United States Department of Agriculture's (USDA) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) maintains a list frame containing all known farms and potential farms in the United States. During Census years, the list frame is frozen and becomes the Census Mail List (CML) for the Census of Agriculture. The CML is incomplete, so NASS uses the June Area Survey (JAS), which is sampled from an independent area frame, to adjust estimates for undercoverage, nonresponse, and misclassification of farms in the Census. A capture-recapture (dual-system estimation) model is used to estimate the adjusted weights assuming conditional independence of the CML and JAS. The USDA's Farm Service Agency (FSA) also maintains a list of farms and potential farms whose owners have participated in a USDA program. The FSA list does not contain all U.S. farms, but it is large enough to be useful in a triple-system estimation model to estimate coverage probabilities for the Census. However, the CML and the FSA list may be dependent, potentially affecting estimates. A triple-system estimation model is proposed, accounting for undercoverage, list dependence (i.e., dependence between coverage probabilities of lists), and nonresponse. Results from simulation studies are presented, and the proposed method is applied to data from the Census of Agriculture.

Key Words: Capture-recapture, Coverage, Nonresponse, List frame, Area frame, Census of Agriculture, Misclassification, Triple-system estimator

1. Introduction

The United States Department of Agriculture's (USDA) National Agricultural Statistics Service (NASS) administers the Census of Agriculture, which is a complete count of U.S. farms and ranches and the people who operate them, once every five years. The most recent Census of Agriculture was conducted in 2022. The Census Mail List (CML), a list frame, is the primary frame used to conduct the Census of Agriculture. However, the CML does not include all farms and ranches in the United States and is therefore subject to undercoverage. In addition, not all producers on the CML respond to the Census of Agriculture, and not all operations on the CML are farms or ranches. Prior to 2022, the Census of Agriculture used a list of potential farms derived from the June Area Survey (JAS), an area-based survey, to account for undercoverage. The list of farms in the JAS sample will be referred to as the JAS list in this paper, but the list consists of a sample from an area frame, not a list frame in and of itself. The Census of Agriculture in 2012 and 2017 used only records on the JAS to estimate coverage, nonresponse, and misclassification probabilities in separate models. A dual-system estimation (DSE) model, which uses two lists to model coverage probabilities of each list, was developed and extended beyond coverage to account jointly for undercoverage, nonresponse, and misclassification in the calculation of weights for the 2022 US Census of Agriculture (Benecha et al., 2022; USDA NASS, 2024). The 2022

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US Census of Agriculture currently uses the DSE model to estimate coverage probabilities using all farms on either the CML or the JAS, a significant advancement over using only farms on the JAS (Benecha et al., 2022).

In addition to the JAS, several large lists are available to NASS that may be used to assess coverage. These are a federal tax list, a CoreLogic parcel list, several large web-based lists, and a list of participants in USDA programs administered by the Farm Service Agency (FSA). It is possible, with one of these lists, to extend the DSE model used in the Census of Agriculture to a triple-system estimation (TSE) model, which uses three lists in a multivariate Bernoulli distribution to estimate coverage probabilities of each list (Zwayne and van der Heijden, 2005). Using FSA data as a third list in a TSE model offers several advantages. This includes better understanding the factors affecting inclusion on the FSA list, a major list-building source for the CML. The ability of producers to participate in USDA programs is constrained by the assistance programs currently available; these programs do not include all crops or livestock. In addition, USDA program participation can vary by race, ethnicity, and religious affiliation (Escalante et al., 2006; Kraybill et al., 2013; Minkoff-Zern and Sloat, 2017). Thus, participation in FSA-administered USDA programs can interact with many other variables known to affect coverage of farms on the CML, including presence of livestock, farm size and type, and demographics. Including FSA as a third list in a TSE model can thus offer additional information to better estimate weights, resulting in lower variances of estimates.

However, using FSA as a third list introduces several challenges. First, a TSE model has not yet been used at NASS, and thus must be developed and tested. Second, there are multiple ways in which the FSA list and CML are dependent, both in terms of overlapping records and in terms of dependent coverage probabilities for each list, such that a model based on conditional independence may not be reasonable. Most FSA records received by NASS are added to the list frame, and many may ultimately be on the CML as well, if they are classified as active farms prior to the CML being developed and frozen. The addition of FSA records to the CML creates a referral scenario that is difficult to account for in multiple-system estimation settings (Jones et al., 2014). Even if FSA records were not referred to the list frame, and thereby integrated into the CML, it is likely that there would still be dependence between the CML and the FSA list, as farms that participate in USDA programs may also be more available for capture via other standard CML list-building sources, such as producer associations and state agency lists. Therefore, a TSE model must be developed that can account for dependence between lists, including dependence stemming from referral. This model uses a multivariate Bernoulli distribution, a form of categorical distribution allowing the dependence between multiple Bernoulli variables to be described (Rota et al., 2016). The multivariate Bernoulli distribution can be used to estimate different list coverage probabilities conditional on the presence or absence of records from other lists (Zwayne and van der Heijden, 2005; Rota et al., 2016).

To fit referred records within a TSE model with list dependence, auxiliary information from the FSA record linkage process is utilized, namely information on whether each record on the CML is linked to an FSA record or was added to the CML from the FSA list. Specifically, FSA records can be used to add and to update records on the list frame. Thus, overlap between the existing CML subset of records from non-FSA sources and an incoming FSA list can be assessed using records that were already on the existing CML, but that were subsequently linked to FSA records. This allows the approximate reconstruction of a list of records that were received from or “could have been received from” FSA, using the results of record linkage techniques to develop the CML from incoming FSA data. After accounting for referral in this way, residual dependence is accounted for within the structure of the multivariate Bernoulli distribution used in the model.

In this paper, a triple-system estimation model is proposed for the Census of Agriculture, using FSA data as a third list with the CML and JAS list. The method to reconstruct the CML from the FSA list is described. The model is introduced and applied to a case study and simulation using Michigan and Missouri data from the 2022 US Census of Agriculture. The objective of the TSE model proposed in this paper is to account for undercoverage, list dependence, and nonresponse, with the possibility of reducing variance relative to the DSE model by providing auxiliary FSA information to improve estimation of weights.

2. Methods

2.1 Data

The TSE model proposed uses three lists: the CML, JAS list, and FSA list. The list of JAS records can be considered independent of the CML and FSA list, as JAS records are not referred onto the CML as FSA records are, and the JAS list consists of a sample of potential farms drawn from an area frame that is constructed independently of the CML. Under the current DSE model, the overlap of the JAS records and CML is assessed using probabilistic record linkage. Specifically, a Fellegi-Sunter model is used for probabilistic record linkage within the program AutoMatch (Broadbent and Iwig, 1999).

The CML is built using a variety of source lists, including producer associations' lists, state license lists (e.g., for nurseries or aquaculture facilities), federal tax lists, and lists of FSA records. The CML does not contain every farm in the United States. The CML also may contain some non-farms, as small operations may be classified as non-farms on the Census of Agriculture if their value of sales falls below \$1,000, even if it was higher previously.

The JAS uses a stratified two-stage random sample design that divides the entire continental United States into strata based on land-use patterns, such as proportion of cropland and urban development. The area frame is complete for the continental United States, and the JAS sample may be considered a random sample of the population of farms.

The FSA maintains a separate list of operations that participate in its programs. USDA programs administered by FSA tend to be focused on specific commodity crops, so the FSA list is not designed to be representative of all types of farms in the United States, as the CML is designed to be, nor is the FSA list based on a random sample like the JAS.

The CML and FSA list have two major sources of dependence, both of which are addressed in this paper. First, the FSA list is used in part to construct the CML, and only CML records and JAS records that do not match CML records are sent a Census questionnaire. Therefore, for the purposes of this paper, the FSA list that would be eligible to be used in a TSE model (i.e., records that received a Census questionnaire) is actually considered a subset of the CML. More specifically, FSA records are matched with records on NASS's list frame using probabilistic record linkage. If an FSA record is matched with an existing list frame record, linkage information is stored to indicate a link between the NASS list frame record ID and the FSA record ID. If an FSA record is not matched with an existing list frame record, the FSA record is added to the list frame as a potential farm, its addition from the FSA list is recorded using a record source ID, and the presence of agriculture is subsequently evaluated using the National Agricultural Classification Survey (NACS). These FSA records may ultimately be included in the CML, if they are classified as having sufficient agriculture to potentially be a farm. However, not every FSA record would be matched with the list frame in time to be included on the CML, and only those FSA records on the CML are currently considered eligible for Census data collection. Thus, the FSA list that would be eligible for Census data collection is reconstructed from the CML using

record source and record linkage information. This is accomplished by splitting the CML into two smaller, overlapping frames, a process described in more detail below.

A second source of dependence between the FSA list and CML is that farms that are added to the CML from other, non-FSA sources may have different coverage probabilities depending on whether or not they were also on the FSA list. For instance, it is possible that farms participating in USDA programs are also more likely to have knowledge of and access to other producers' associations and farm networks that may be used as non-FSA list-building sources. This possible dependence is addressed using a proposed multivariate Bernoulli likelihood.

2.2 Methods summary

The process of reconstructing an FSA Census-eligible list by splitting the CML into overlapping frames is described. A coverage model is first described without the inclusion of response probabilities, to first introduce the idea of the multivariate Bernoulli likelihood for the coverage model component of the TSE model. The model is then extended to account for response probability; this model including both coverage and response probabilities is the TSE model ultimately proposed. Finally, a data analysis and simulation are conducted to compare the proposed TSE model and the existing DSE model using 2022 US Census of Agriculture data.

2.3 Using frames to account for FSA referral onto CML

Under NASS's current record linkage approach, almost every FSA record that is provided to NASS is linked or added to the list frame. For each FSA record, this record linkage process can either result in a link between an FSA record and an existing list frame record, or an FSA record being added to the list frame as a potential farm. Under traditional multiple-system estimation modeling, if the CML and FSA lists were to be modeled separately, this would pose a problem sometimes known as referral, where every record (or a large number of records) from one list is deliberately added to another list. In this instance, this creates a problem where the probability of being on the CML conditional on being on the FSA list would approach one, which would lead to unreasonably high or low estimates of parameters before they are logit-transformed.

To address this problem, the following aspect of FSA record linkage is used: if an FSA record is found on the list frame, the FSA record is linked to that list frame record in a record update, rather than a new record being created. FSA records that were not previously on the list frame are added to the list frame as potential farms, and a record source ID is generated indicating their source as FSA data. The list frame, and consequently the CML, can thus be divided into two parts: those records that were added via historical, non-FSA-specific list-building approaches (e.g., state agency lists, producer association lists – the historical-sourced frame, hereafter “historical”), and those records which might have been added via an FSA list (“FSA-sourced” frame, hereafter “FSA”). The records on the second list are all associated in some way with an FSA record, either by linkage or by being a criteria record added from FSA directly. This division of the CML into two frames divides CML records into three categories that can be used to assess the overlap between these two frames. The first category includes records that were added via historical list-building approaches, and which do not have any linked FSA data. The second category includes records that were added from an FSA list. The third category includes records that were added via historical list-building, but that were subsequently linked to an FSA record. This third category represents the overlap between the two frames, because these records were added to the list frame via historical list-building, but they might have been added to the

list frame via an FSA list if they were not previously on the list frame, since they were associated with an FSA record that NASS received (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Visual representation of dividing the CML into two overlapping frames (historical and FSA).

The historical and FSA frames combined collectively make up the original CML (Figure 1 and Figure 2), and thus as a whole they have the same underlying data collection structure, in that records on both frames are eligible to be sent a Census of Agriculture questionnaire. However, the two frames differ from each other with regard to sampling structure. The historical frame consists of records found using a variety of list sources and is meant to be as comprehensive as possible. Thus, for the purposes of meeting TSE assumptions, the historical frame may be considered a relatively random sample of the underlying population of farms, as the JAS list is. The FSA frame is more likely to contain certain commodity crop farms than livestock farms, since commodity crops are the focus of many USDA programs. The dependence structure between lists proposed in the TSE model may partially account for the non-random nature of the FSA frame, as FSA coverage probabilities can be modified based on the presence or absence of specific farm types on the historical frame. In future Censuses, it is also possible that the FSA frame will form an increasingly representative sample of farms as USDA programs expand to serve a larger variety of crops, livestock, and locations (e.g., urban areas; USDA, 2023).

Figure 2: Visual representation of the lists used in the TSE model, with the full CML divided into historical and FSA frames. As these are overlapping subsets of the CML, they may overlap with JAS.

2.4 Basic coverage model (excluding response)

This model is an application of the method proposed by Zwayne and van der Heijden (2005), though to describe and interpret aspects of the likelihood, we reference Rota et al. (2016). Using the terminology of Rota et al. (2016), the TSE likelihood can be written as a multivariate Bernoulli (MVB) distribution. Let $\mathbf{y} = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$ represent the capture history of a given record on the historical (1), JAS (2), and FSA (3) lists, respectively. Because each of the captures on the lists has two possible outcomes (1 for capture or 0 for non-capture), there are $2^3 = 8$ different possible combinations of the combined capture history vector \mathbf{y} , namely

$$\{(1, 1, 1), (1, 1, 0), (1, 0, 1), (1, 0, 0), (0, 1, 1), (0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1), (0, 0, 0)\}.$$

This combined capture history \mathbf{y} is distributed as

$$\mathbf{y} \sim \text{MVB}(\pi_{111}, \pi_{110}, \pi_{101}, \pi_{100}, \pi_{011}, \pi_{010}, \pi_{001}, \pi_{000}),$$

where π_{111} is the probability that a record is present on all three lists, π_{110} is the probability that a record is present on the historical (1) and JAS (2) lists but not the FSA (3) list, and so on.

The likelihood of \mathbf{y} is

$$f(\mathbf{y} | \pi_{111}, \pi_{110}, \pi_{101}, \pi_{100}, \pi_{011}, \pi_{010}, \pi_{001}, \pi_{000}) = \pi_{111}^{c_1 c_2 c_3} \pi_{110}^{c_1 c_2 (1-c_3)} \pi_{101}^{c_1 (1-c_2) c_3} \pi_{100}^{c_1 (1-c_2) (1-c_3)} \pi_{011}^{(1-c_1) c_2 c_3} \pi_{010}^{(1-c_1) c_2 (1-c_3)} \pi_{001}^{(1-c_1) (1-c_2) c_3} \pi_{000}^{(1-c_1) (1-c_2) (1-c_3)},$$

and it can be rearranged by taking the log to derive the following combinations of coverage probabilities, which Rota et al. (2016) call natural parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{100}}{\pi_{000}} \right), \\ f_2 &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{010}}{\pi_{000}} \right), \\ f_3 &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{001}}{\pi_{000}} \right), \\ f_{12} &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{110} \pi_{000}}{\pi_{100} \pi_{010}} \right), \\ f_{13} &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{101} \pi_{000}}{\pi_{100} \pi_{001}} \right), \\ f_{23} &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{011} \pi_{000}}{\pi_{010} \pi_{001}} \right), \\ f_{123} &= \log \left(\frac{\pi_{111} \pi_{100} \pi_{010} \pi_{001}}{\pi_{110} \pi_{101} \pi_{011} \pi_{000}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

These natural parameters can be modeled as functions of covariates (x) and parameters (θ), e.g.,

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= x_\alpha^\top \theta_\alpha, \\ f_2 &= x_\beta^\top \theta_\beta, \\ &\vdots \end{aligned}$$

Rota et al. (2016) describe in detail various derived marginal probabilities, conditional probabilities, and interpretations of natural parameters for the case of two lists; some of the possible derived quantities and interpretations are briefly summarized in the context of three lists.

First, setting natural parameters that control interactions, e.g., $f_{12} = 0$, implies pairwise independence (e.g., between Lists 1 and 2 in this case). This property can be used in model testing and selection to determine whether lists are independent by comparing models where, for instance, f_{12} is set to zero and models where parameters for f_{12} are estimated (Rota et al., 2016). In the case of the Census of Agriculture data analysis conducted in this paper, only the f_1 , f_2 , f_3 , and f_{13} natural parameters are linked to covariates, as only historical-FSA list dependence is expected.

Probabilities of different capture histories (e.g., π_{111} , π_{110}) can be calculated using a multinomial logit link. Specifically, the following equation can be used to map natural parameters to probabilities using a design matrix:

$$[\pi_{111} \quad \pi_{110} \quad \pi_{101} \quad \pi_{100} \quad \pi_{011} \quad \pi_{010} \quad \pi_{001} \quad \pi_{000}] = \frac{e^\eta}{\sum e^\eta},$$

where

$$\eta = [f_1 \quad f_2 \quad f_3 \quad f_{12} \quad f_{13} \quad f_{23} \quad f_{123}] \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

and $\sum e^\eta$ is a sum over the exponentiated vector e^η . In order to enforce independence, the rows of the design matrix corresponding to natural parameters involving multiple lists, such as f_{12} , may be set to zero.

Marginal probabilities may be derived by summing over the individual probabilities, e.g.,

$$\Pr(c_1 = 1) = \pi_{111} + \pi_{110} + \pi_{101} + \pi_{100}.$$

Full conditional probabilities of coverage can be derived, for instance, as

$$\Pr(c_1 = 1 | c_2, c_3) = \frac{\pi_{1c_2c_3}}{\pi_{1c_2c_3} + \pi_{0c_2c_3}}.$$

More specifically, as Rota et al. (2016) note, conditional probabilities have a relationship with natural parameters that eases interpretation, e.g.:

$$\Pr(c_1 = 1 | c_2 = 0, c_3 = 0) = \frac{\pi_{100}}{\pi_{100} + \pi_{000}} = \text{logit}^{-1}(f_1)$$

$$\Pr(c_1 = 1 | c_2 = 0, c_3 = 1) = \frac{\pi_{101}}{\pi_{101} + \pi_{001}} = \text{logit}^{-1}(f_1 + f_{13}).$$

In this example, the parameters of f_1 can be interpreted as governing the conditional probability of a record being present on List 1, given its absence on Lists 2 and 3, while the parameters of f_{13} can be interpreted as modifying the parameters of f_1 when a record is present on List 3. The model parametrization using natural parameters allows relationships between coverage probabilities and covariates to differ based on dependence with other lists. For example, using this model, it would be possible to investigate whether the total acres of a farm or the presence or amount of a major commodity (e.g., corn, cattle) on a farm affects presence of a farm on the historical list (frame) differently, conditional on whether the farm is also on the FSA list.

2.5 Likelihood of coverage model (without considering response)

Let $y_i = k$ be the capture history of record $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_{\text{observed}}$, with

$$k \in \{(1, 1, 1), (1, 1, 0), (1, 0, 1), (1, 0, 0), (0, 1, 1), (0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 1), (0, 0, 0)\}$$

having $K = 8$ possible outcomes, and let π be a $n_{\text{observed}} \times K$ with $\pi_{i,k}$ being the cell-specific probability that record i has capture history k and π_i being the i -th row of π . Let θ be the parameter vectors of coefficients of covariates and \mathbf{X} be the one or more design matrices of covariates (the dimensions of θ and \mathbf{X} may vary for different natural parameters). Because observation is conditional on a record being captured on any list, the likelihood is conditioned on each record being captured at least once:

$$L(\pi, \theta | \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{X}) = \prod_{i=1}^{n_{\text{observed}}} \frac{\pi_{i,y_i}}{1 - \pi_{i,000}},$$

where $y_i = k$ in the subscript of π_{i,y_i} and π_{i,y_i} and $\pi_{i,000}$ are functions of θ and \mathbf{X} .

Once maximum likelihood estimates for θ are calculated, the triple-system estimator using all observed records is calculated as the reciprocal of each record's estimated sample inclusion probability:

$$\hat{N} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{observed}}} \frac{1}{1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,000}}.$$

This estimator uses all available records, and is derived from summing the reciprocal of each record's overall probability of capture by any list, which is the complement of its capture on no lists ($\hat{\pi}_{i,000}$). This does not account for the response rate of records or the use of only CML farms in the Census estimates. This differs from the previous DSE model used in the Census of Agriculture, in which only CML respondents' records are weighted and summed. Therefore, an alternative model and estimator weighting only Census respondents on the CML is described below.

2.6 Considering the inclusion of response probability

To include response probabilities in the model, the following assumptions are made. Let $\rho_{i,1}$ be the response probability for records on the historical frame, with $\rho_{i,2}$ and $\rho_{i,3}$ the response probabilities for JAS and FSA records, respectively. First, it is assumed that $\rho_{i,2}$ is equal to one. Records on any of the CML, JAS list, or FSA list may not respond to the Census questionnaire. However, in order for $\rho_{i,1}$ to be estimated, a key part of the Census weighting process, a fixed value must be assumed for $\rho_{i,2}$, so that nonresponse on the CML list can be observed and modeled when a record on the JAS list and the CML does not respond to the Census. Given that sufficient data are collected from the June Area Survey to estimate response probability $\rho_{i,1}$ in this case, it is safe to assume that $\rho_{i,2} = 1$. While certain variables are required to be reported to FSA, these are not as comprehensive as those reported on the JAS. Thus, $\rho_{i,3}$ cannot necessarily be set to one. Second, it is assumed that $\rho_{i,1} = \rho_{i,3}$ – that is, that historical and FSA records have equal Census response probabilities. Therefore, the response probability is rewritten simply as ρ_i . Third, if a record is only on the CML (historical or FSA frames) and does not respond, no data are collected on that record. This limits the range of possible combinations of coverage and response. More specifically, let $\mathbf{y}^* = (c_1, c_2, c_3, r_1)$ represent the capture history of a given record on the historical (c_1), JAS (c_2), and FSA (c_3) lists and response ($r_1 = 1$) or nonresponse ($r_1 = 0$) of a record on the CML, respectively. Under the referral model, \mathbf{y}^* follows a categorical

distribution limited by response probability:

$$\mathbf{y}^* \sim \text{Categorical}(\pi_{111}\rho_i, \pi_{110}\rho_i, \pi_{101}\rho_i, \pi_{100}\rho_i, \pi_{011}\rho_i, \pi_{010}, \\ \pi_{001}\rho_i, \pi_{111}(1 - \rho_i), \pi_{110}(1 - \rho_i), \pi_{011}(1 - \rho_i))$$

Note that there are now four unobserved outcomes

$$\{(1, 0, 0, 0), (0, 0, 1, 0), (1, 0, 1, 0), (0, 0, 0, 0)\}.$$

Suppose there are n_{observed}^* records that fall in the universe of possible combinations of coverage and response. Then the likelihood developed by including response probability is

$$L(\pi^*, \theta | \mathbf{y}^*, \mathbf{X}) = \prod_{i=1}^{n_{\text{observed}}^*} \frac{\pi_{i,y_i^*}^*}{1 - \pi_{i,0000}^* - \pi_{i,1000}^* - \pi_{i,0010}^* - \pi_{i,1010}^*},$$

where the denominator is equal to the sum of

$$\pi^* = (\pi_{111}\rho_i, \pi_{110}\rho_i, \pi_{101}\rho_i, \pi_{100}\rho_i, \pi_{011}\rho_i, \pi_{010}, \pi_{001}\rho_i, \pi_{111}(1 - \rho_i), \pi_{110}(1 - \rho_i), \pi_{011}(1 - \rho_i)).$$

This likelihood yields an updated triple-system estimator of

$$\hat{N}^* = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{observed}}^*} \frac{1}{1 - \pi_{i,0000}^* - \pi_{i,1000}^* - \pi_{i,0010}^* - \pi_{i,1010}^*}.$$

The estimator that would be used during the Census sums joint probabilities of coverage on the CML (i.e., coverage on the historical and FSA frames combined, \mathcal{C}) and response (\mathcal{R}):

$$\hat{N}^* = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{C} \cap \mathcal{R}} \frac{1}{\hat{\pi}_{i,1111}^* + \hat{\pi}_{i,1101}^* + \hat{\pi}_{i,1011}^* + \hat{\pi}_{i,1001}^* + \hat{\pi}_{i,0111}^* + \hat{\pi}_{i,0011}^*}.$$

This referral scenario is suitable when a major list-building source is 1) used both to add records to a list frame and to update or enhance records already on the list frame, and 2) able to be identified on the larger list frame using record source information. For example, if an address-based frame is constructed using postal service records, and then supplemented with tax information, but tax information is sometimes linked to existing postal service records (e.g., to impute income on surveys), the tax information records have been referred to the postal service list. However, assuming record sources indicate which records came from tax information, and assuming linkage is reliable, the list of records that might have been added to the list frame using tax information can be reconstructed.

One important assumption of the referral model is that the FSA list can only be reconstructed from the list frame or CML, and not from the JAS list. This may not necessarily be the case, as many FSA records have associated Common Land Units (CLUs), spatial records of specific land ownership and operating arrangements, that can spatially overlap JAS tracts, which represent unique ownership and operating arrangements within sampled JAS segments. If it is assumed that sufficiently overlapping JAS tracts and FSA CLUs have the same owner-operator arrangement, these FSA and JAS records might be considered linked. If they are not on the CML, the referral model would have to be extended further to account for cases when FSA records are found in the JAS data but may not occur on the CML's FSA frame. These FSA records, since they were found in the JAS but not the CML, would have a response probability of one and would represent a different category than the "011" category under the referral model (a CML record that was added via an FSA list, and was also found in JAS).

2.7 Case study and simulation using 2022 US Census of Agriculture

A two-part approach is employed to test the TSE model, using 2022 US Census of Agriculture data. First, the TSE model and the currently used DSE model (described in Benecha et al., 2022) are fit to selected states' data, and estimates of total farms and variances are calculated. Weights are not constrained, and these totals are uncalibrated unlike those published in the final 2022 US Census of Agriculture results. Therefore, extremely large weights are a possible artefact of the models used, particularly in the presence of known model misspecification (e.g., a model with independent lists fit to data simulated with dependent lists). Second, a simulation scenario is run and analyzed, in which data are simulated from the TSE model's coverage and response probabilities, and both the TSE and DSE models are fit to the simulated data. This is done to assess the effects of list dependence on sampling variability of the dual-system estimator, and to determine whether using a triple-system estimator reduces this variability. Both of the variance estimations for the case study and the simulation scenario use parametric bootstrapping, though the exact role of parametric bootstrapping is different for these two analyses.

An analysis of data from the 2022 US Census of Agriculture is conducted for two states: Michigan and Missouri. These two states are chosen because both have a relatively high diversity of farm types, and consequently neither very high nor very low rates of USDA program enrollment. On the one hand, Michigan and Missouri both fall within the United States' major corn- and soy-growing regions; thus, both states contain large numbers of grain producers, who are major users of USDA programs. On the other hand, both states also contain relatively large numbers of farms that are less likely to participate in USDA programs administered by FSA, such as livestock farms, fruit farms, and farms operated by Anabaptist (e.g., Amish) producers (Kraybill et al., 2013).

Because the "frame" approach used to assess FSA coverage uses the existing CML as the baseline for developing frames, the linked CML-JAS dataset for the 2022 US Census of Agriculture can be used for analysis. No new FSA records are added relative to those included in the 2022 Census; instead, records are enriched with FSA linkage information. Specifically, FSA records on the CML are assigned to one of two different subsets — those that were added to the CML directly from the FSA list (implying that they were not on the historical frame but were on the FSA frame), and those that were on the CML already but subsequently linked to an FSA record (implying that they were on both the historical and FSA frames). FSA records added directly to the CML are identified using a specific record source ID on the list frame, and records with this record source ID are updated such that the record is listed as being on the FSA frame but not on the historical frame. To update FSA linkage information for those records on both the historical and FSA frames, a specific record linkage table is used. This record linkage table includes, for each FSA record, both the original NASS list frame record with which it was matched, and the "best" NASS list frame record with which to match the FSA record. In many cases, these NASS list frame records are the same. For instance, for a record associated with a single operator owning a single operation, there is only one NASS person and operation with which an FSA match could have occurred, so the NASS records listed for this FSA record (original and "best") would be identical. However, where an FSA record originally matched with a partner in an operation, but the "best" match would be with the principal producer of that operation (i.e., the person likely to be sent a questionnaire by NASS), the original and "best" NASS records would be different. If the NASS list frame ID for a CML record is found in either the original or "best" part of the table, that CML record is updated as being on both the historical and FSA frame. This process does not necessarily account for every single linkage between every single FSA and NASS list frame record. However, this

does account for FSA linkages for the NASS list frame records most likely to appear on the CML, namely those that are generally most eligible for sampling in NASS’s surveys and therefore very likely to appear in the “best” portion of the NASS-FSA linkage table.

To compare the TSE model with the current DSE model used in the Census of Agriculture, all models in both the case study and the simulation scenario are fit using TensorFlow version 2.11.0 in Python version 3.8.19 using custom layers for coverage and response probabilities and Census weights. The TSE model includes historical-only, JAS-only, FSA-only, historical-FSA interaction, and response link functions. The dual-system model includes CML, JAS, and response link functions. The DSE model fit here does not exactly match the model used in the Census of Agriculture, in two major ways. First, calibration and rounding of weights are not employed here. Second, neither the DSE nor the TSE model used here accounts for misclassification, so the small group of misclassified records in the study area is excluded from the case study for Michigan and Missouri and from the simulation scenario.

For the case study and subsequent simulation scenario, the data needed for the DSE model can be recovered from the data used in the TSE model (true data in the case of the case study; simulated data in the case of the simulation scenario) using a simple reformatting procedure. To reformat the data to be used in the DSE model, another version of each dataset is created that collapses the historical and FSA frames back together, to re-form the CML in the selected states. The TSE model is fit to the original data, and the DSE model is fit to the reformatted data.

Parametric bootstrapping (Sartore et al., 2022) is used to estimate the variance of the triple-system and dual-system estimators for the case study, and to estimate simulated sampling variability of the triple-system and dual-system estimators for the simulation scenario. The parametric bootstrapping approach differs between the case study and simulation scenario in the underlying model from which bootstrapped datasets are generated. For the case study, bootstrapped datasets are generated from the TSE model to derive the variance of the total farms estimate, and from the DSE model to derive the variance of the total farms estimate. For the simulation scenario, bootstrapped datasets are generated from the TSE model fit to the underlying simulation population (the 2022 US Census of Agriculture data for Michigan), to create a scenario in which list dependence is present in the datasets used for estimation.

The parametric bootstrapping procedure for the TSE model is similar in the case study and simulation scenario, in every aspect except the underlying model from which data are generated and the subset of records weighted to produce estimates. For each bootstrap replicate $b = 1, 2, \dots, B$, overall estimated inclusion probabilities $(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,000})$ for each observed record are used to simulate inclusion values $z_{i,b}$ for record i and bootstrap replicate b , such that

$$z_{i,b} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,000}).$$

For included records ($z_{i,b} = 1$), observed coverage and response categories $\tilde{y}_{i,b}$ are simulated using estimated observation probabilities that are a function of $\hat{\pi}_i$ and $\hat{\rho}_i$ (e.g., probability of observing a particular coverage and response outcome, conditional on inclusion in the sample), such that

$$\tilde{y}_{i,b} \sim \text{Categorical}(\hat{\pi}_{i,111}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,110}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,101}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,100}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,011}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,010}, \hat{\pi}_{i,001}\hat{\rho}_i, \hat{\pi}_{i,111}(1 - \hat{\rho}_i), \hat{\pi}_{i,110}(1 - \hat{\rho}_i), \hat{\pi}_{i,011}(1 - \hat{\rho}_i)).$$

Note that these probabilities are already conditional on inclusion in the TSE model, as these represent outcomes that can only be observed. For both the case study and the simulation scenario, this results in subsamples of the original records, with covariates held

fixed but with new observed coverage and response outcomes generated, to which TSE and DSE models are subsequently fit. For the case study, all originally observed records are weighted and summed to yield total estimates using bootstrapped modeled weights, whereas for the simulation scenario, only the records subsampled in each bootstrap iteration are weighted and summed to produce total estimates. All weighted estimates are produced by summing joint probabilities of CML coverage and response only over CML respondents. This sum is over only subsampled records for each bootstrap replicate in the simulation scenario, and over all CML respondents when estimating variance for the case study.

The parametric bootstrapping procedure for the DSE model, used to estimate the total farms variance in the DSE model, is similar to that of the TSE model, except that inclusion probabilities and observation probabilities are changed to account for the underlying lists being only CML and JAS, not CML, JAS, and FSA. Specifically, defining $\hat{\pi}_{i,C}$, $\hat{\pi}_{i,A}$, and $\hat{\pi}_{i,R}$ as the CML coverage, JAS coverage, and response probabilities derived from the DSE model, the inclusion probability used to generate $z_{i,b}$ is now

$$\hat{\pi}_{i,A}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,C}) + \hat{\pi}_{i,C}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,A})\hat{\pi}_{i,R} + \hat{\pi}_{i,C}\hat{\pi}_{i,A}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,R}) + \hat{\pi}_{i,C}\hat{\pi}_{i,A}\hat{\pi}_{i,R},$$

and observed coverage and response outcomes $\tilde{o}_{i,b} \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ are simulated from

$$\tilde{o}_{i,b} \sim \text{Categorical}(\hat{\pi}_{i,A}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,C}), \hat{\pi}_{i,C}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,A})\hat{\pi}_{i,R}, \hat{\pi}_{i,C}\hat{\pi}_{i,A}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i,R}), \hat{\pi}_{i,C}\hat{\pi}_{i,A}\hat{\pi}_{i,R}).$$

For the purposes of the simulation scenario, the underlying population consists of the 2022 US Census of Agriculture data from Michigan. The records and covariates in the population remain fixed. What varies between simulation replicates is whether each record is included in the replicate. If it is included in the replicate, observed coverage and response category are determined conditionally on inclusion variables.

For the case study and the simulation scenario, the same covariates are used in the historical-only, JAS-only, FSA-only, historical-FSA interaction, and response link functions (f_1 , f_2 , f_3 , f_{13} , and ρ , respectively) in the TSE model, and in the CML, JAS, and response link functions in the DSE model. These covariates include total land, cropland, cattle, farm type (an internal classification used by NASS), and indicator variables of operations having any female, nonwhite, or Hispanic/Latino producers.

In interpreting results and comparing them to published US Census of Agriculture results, it must be emphasized that no constraints, rounding, or calibration are used to control the values of weights, in either the simulation or case study. This can result in extremely large weights that can be influenced by starting parameter values, extreme values of covariates (e.g., large amounts of land operated or owned, but no cropland, as in certain large livestock farms), and model misspecification (i.e., assuming conditional independence when dependent data are simulated). The effect of extreme covariate values can be further increased by the method of simulating bootstrapped datasets. The bootstrapping method used is more likely to include records with covariate values associated with higher probabilities of inclusion. As records with more extreme covariate values (and often lower probabilities of inclusion) are included in bootstrapped datasets in smaller quantities. These covariate values are likely to become more extreme relative to the distribution of the other subsampled records' covariates, causing weights to inflate further. It is likely that both the TSE and DSE models would perform better during the final production of the US Census of Agriculture than they would in this preliminary analysis. Ultimately, integer calibration and different variance estimation methods would be used to limit the influence of extremely large weights.

For the case study, estimates of total farms and variance are calculated, and the total farms estimate is reported with a symmetric 95% bootstrap quantile interval. For the simulation scenario, bias is calculated as $(\bar{N}/N - 1) \star 100\%$, where \bar{N} is the mean of the

estimates of total farms for bootstrap replicates, and N is the true number of total farms in the simulated population. A symmetric 95% bootstrap quantile interval is also reported.

3. Results

3.1 Simulation

The total “population” size for the simulation is the number of Michigan farms included in the 2022 US Census of Agriculture TSE model, namely 24,048 farms. This serves as the true population size for the simulation because each bootstrap replicate is simulated as a sample of this population, and then reweighted up to the true population total for the population from which subsamples are simulated. For 500 simulated datasets, the mean population total estimate for the TSE model is 38,020 (58% bias), and 91,897 (282% bias) for the DSE model. For the full 500 simulated datasets, the 95% quantile range was narrower for the TSE model than for the DSE model, which showed evidence of estimates driven by extremely large weights (Table 1). The results for both models may be affected by extreme weights that can be corrected by calibration. Assuming that estimates over 75,000 are likely caused by datasets with extreme values, when these datasets are removed (one dataset for TSE, 160 datasets for DSE), the mean population total estimate for the TSE model is 24,552 (2% bias), and 51,996 (116% bias) for the DSE model. For the smaller number of simulated datasets, the 95% quantile range was still narrower for the TSE model than for the DSE model (Table 2 and Figure 3).

	Triple-system estimator	Dual-system estimator
Bias in total farms	58%	282%
Simulation 2.5% quantile	21,408	37,751
Simulation 97.5% quantile	32,801	272,734

Table 1: Bias and simulation 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles for 500 simulated datasets. The datasets are simulated from the TSE model fit to Michigan data, and the triple-system estimator (left) and dual-system estimator (right) are fit to the resulting simulated data.

	Triple-system estimator	Dual-system estimator
Bias in total farms	2%	116%
Simulation 2.5% quantile	21,407	37,329
Simulation 97.5% quantile	32,413	72,847

Table 2: Bias, simulation 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles, and coefficients of variation (CVs) for simulated datasets with total estimates greater than 75,000 removed. The datasets are simulated from the TSE model fit to Michigan data, and the triple-system estimator (left) and dual-system estimator (right) are fit to the resulting simulated data.

It is important to note that the performance of the DSE model in the face of simulated dependence in data does not invalidate the DSE model’s performance on the US Census of Agriculture. First, data for the simulation are generated under the assumption that the TSE model, with its underlying dependence structure, is the “true” model. This does not mean that this TSE model is the best-fitting model for the US Census of Agriculture data. The simulation in no way provides evidence that the TSE model used to simulate data is the actual best-fitting model. This model is also not applied to real data in the simulation, and relatively few covariates have been included, and no calibration or rounding has been performed to assess the performance of finalized estimates. In addition, the calibration

Figure 3: Distributions of total farms estimates from simulated datasets (with total estimates greater than 75,000 removed). Both triple-system estimators (left) and dual-system estimators (right) are fit. The vertical red line is at 24,048, the number of observed farms in Michigan in the 2022 US Census of Agriculture, and used as population size in the simulation.

algorithm used in the US Census of Agriculture (Sartore et al., 2019) includes the possibility of upper and lower bounds, including known weight restrictions that should be put in place (e.g., self-representing records that are extremely large operations, or other known influential operations). None of these constraints were used in the simulation. Even in the face of model misspecification and associated bias, the presence of bounds in the calibration algorithm would likely reduce bias from misspecified models substantially.

3.2 Case study

The total number of farms in Michigan in the final 2022 US Census of Agriculture is 45,581. The TSE model fit to Michigan data without calibration or misclassified farms yielded an estimate of 44,610 farms, with a 95% bootstrap interval of 34,619–91,733 based on 500 bootstrapped datasets. The DSE model yielded an estimate of 46,852 farms, with a 95% bootstrap interval of 34,371–112,385 based on 500 bootstrapped datasets.

The total number of farms in Missouri in the final 2022 US Census of Agriculture is 87,887. The TSE model fit to Missouri data without calibration or misclassified farms yielded an estimate of 109,142 farms, with a 95% bootstrap interval of 85,698–179,022 based on 500 bootstrapped datasets. The DSE model yielded an estimate of 113,860 farms, with a 95% bootstrap interval of 91,541–211,805 based on 500 bootstrapped datasets.

4. Discussion

The TSE model may potentially enhance the existing DSE model for the Census of Agriculture by better accounting for the effect of USDA program participation on Census weights. When the TSE and DSE models are applied to the data from Michigan and Missouri, they give similar point estimates, with the TSE model slightly outperforming the DSE model in terms of standard error. When data are simulated under the assumed dependence structure of the Census data in the TSE model, where historical-sourced and FSA frame coverage probabilities are dependent, the TSE model outperforms the DSE model in terms of bias and standard error. Recording FSA participation of farms as a separate list provides additional

information to improve weight estimation, and results in reduced variability in weights under the TSE model relative to the DSE model. The DSE model collapses the historical and FSA frames back into the CML, missing the underlying structure that can cause differences in weights within farm types, demographic groups, and other subgroups based on FSA participation. The simulation shows that the DSE model may not perform well in the face of strong list dependence, but the case study does not necessarily show evidence of strong list dependence or associated bias, as point estimates from triple-system and DSE models are similar. Instead, the case study shows the potential of using a TSE model to provide more detailed information on list frame records with different record source and linkage histories, some of which may have had more opportunities to be added to the list frame than others (e.g., if they were on both the historical and FSA frames, instead of just one).

Further steps are required to yield the final farm total estimates used in the Census of Agriculture. Integer calibration (Sartore et al., 2019) must be performed, and misclassification must either be modeled, or the removal of misclassified farms from the model must be justified. Integer calibration is the likely next step in research on the TSE model, as datasets and models used to perform calibration already exist at NASS and can likely be easily adapted for the TSE model. The model may also be adapted to account for misclassification by including more observable categories in the response variable. However, accounting for misclassification and including misclassified farms in the model may not be necessary, if it can be shown that the probabilities of non-farms being classified as farms and the probabilities of farms being classified as non-farms are roughly equal. This seems likely in many cases, as misclassification is most likely for small operations with value of sales around \$1,000, where only a few hundred dollars' increase, or decrease may cause misclassification.

Treating the FSA list as an entirely separate list from the CML would be impossible, due to the referral of most FSA records received by NASS onto the list frame. The data structure used for the TSE model avoids the referral problem by splitting the CML into two overlapping frames, consisting of records that were added from historical sources or records that were added or could have been added from FSA sources. The overlap between these two frames is possible because FSA records are used both to add new records to the list frame and to update and link FSA data to existing records. This approach could therefore be extended for any source list that is used both to add records to the list frame and to provide linkage data for existing records, even if those linkage data are used for other purposes besides coverage modeling, such as imputation.

The use of smaller frames to split the CML also creates the possibility of modeling coverage without the use of JAS data. However, adjustments to how nonresponse is modeled would be necessary. The existing approach is to model response probability based on overlapped CML-JAS records, and whether they responded to the Census of Agriculture after being included in the JAS. This allows the modeled response probabilities to be based on data collected during the Census year, rather than potentially much older control data. The nonresponse model could be adjusted to include older control data, in which case Census nonrespondents who were not in JAS could be included in the model. Because this is likely undesirable due to the potential age of control data, FSA could potentially be used in the place of JAS data to model nonresponse. Because FSA data are required to be collected for program participation, the response probability of the FSA list could be assumed to be one, assuming every FSA record had data available for the Census year. This would limit response covariates only to those which would be available for FSA records that did not respond to the Census of Agriculture; this would be a much more limited set than the set of covariates available for Census modeling, because FSA may not ask for certain items (e.g.,

specific crops, livestock, or management practices) at all, or may collect and report certain data in different ways. If misclassification were included in the model, how it was estimated would also have to be adjusted, as currently JAS data are used to model misclassification.

Additional aspects of modeling would need to be addressed if the JAS data were not included in a potential coverage model. First, there is a possibility that certain historical frame records would have a systematically low or zero probability of having FSA linkage, and therefore FSA coverage, potentially making modeling more difficult for these records. These sorts of records might include, among other subgroups, specific specialty crop or livestock farms and certain farms operated by Amish producers, as Amish producers participate in USDA programs at very low rates (Kraybill et al., 2013). FSA may not be as effective a data source for modeling coverage of these sorts of records without JAS, although the inclusion of relevant covariates or a penalized likelihood may help (Clipp et al., 2021). Second, it is unknown whether list dependence could be modeled well using only two lists. Dependence between occupancy parameters of two species, in a model with an almost identical likelihood, can be estimated under certain conditions (Rota et al., 2016), but further research would be required.

Including FSA data in Census modeling, for the purposes of coverage modeling and even imputation, can be highly beneficial. However, inclusion of FSA data does pose additional challenges. The timing of FSA data collection relative to important Census of Agriculture timelines (e.g., the date on which the CML is developed, or the date on which modeling is begun) can affect estimates by affecting the amount of linkage data available. Care would have to be taken to ensure that FSA data were linked to the list frame in a timely manner, so that as much linkage data would be available for Census modeling as possible. There is also more than one way to record FSA linkage. This analysis uses a table recording both the “best” list frame record and the original list frame record linked to each FSA record, but that table, while it records most FSA linkages that would be present in the CML, likely does not record every FSA linkage.

The TSE model proposed is unusual in fitting a capture-recapture model in a software with the potential for a neural network model, namely TensorFlow. The use of TensorFlow for this form of model creates additional opportunities for variable interactions and selection beyond the standard, linear-model-based approaches typically used in capture-recapture models. Additional layers may be added to create covariate interaction terms, and dropout layers or penalized likelihoods may be used to constrain parameter estimates or retain only the most relevant variables. The effects of these and similar adaptations on estimates is an area of ongoing research.

5. Conclusion

The TSE model offers additional information relative to the existing DSE model, leading to gains in bias and variability of estimates of total farms in the presence of list dependence. In addition, the model used to reconstruct referred lists such as the FSA list from larger frames can be applied to other scenarios in which a list is used both to add to and to update the primary sampling frame. Building the model using a neural network offers additional opportunities for more sophisticated modeling approaches.

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